

ISic1656

I.Sicily inscription 1656

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 15569 + 14609

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Ἐνθάδε γώτινιεύ]τύχη τὸ σῶ[μακαθίζω]
2. [οὔτ]ω πρόσκερον ἀεὶ
3. [τὸ ἄθλον τυ]ραννικὸν τῆς ὕλης ἐπέσχον [θεεῖω]
4. [Λόγω ἕως οὐτῶ ἀσωμάτων δεσπότη]
5. [τὸ ἦτορ ἀ]σώματον ἐχώρησα

Apparatus

Text after Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645093

Bibliography

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Orsi, P. 1896. Gli scavi a S. Giovanni a Siracusa. *Römische Quartalschrift für christliche Alterthumskunde und für Kirchengeschichte*. 10: 1-59. At 209 no.3

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1656. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354747>